

In the network of online money

Condensed version of the TA-SWISS study, «New digital Swiss francs - our money of the future»

TA-SWISS, the Foundation for Technology Assessment and a centre for excellence of the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences, deals with the opportunities and risks of new technologies.

This condensed version is based on a scientific study carried out on behalf of TA-SWISS by an interdisciplinary project team under the leadership of Corinne Zellweger-Gutknecht (University of Basel, Faculty of Law). The condensed version presents the most important results and conclusions of the study for a broad audience.

Team members: Dr. Sandra Stupar, Hochschule Luzern, Institut für Finanzdienstleistungen Zug, Prof. Dr. Michael Derrer, Hochschule Luzern, Institut für Betriebs- und Regionalökonomie, Dr. Virgile Perret, Observatoire de la Finance, Prof. Dr. Paul H. Dembinski, University of Fribourg and Observatoire de la Finance, Prof. Dr. Corinne Zellweger-Gutknecht, University of Basel, Prof. Dr. Cornelia Stengel, Kellerhals Carrard

Condensed version of the TA-SWISS study «Neue Digitale Franken. Unser Geld der Zukunft?»

Corinne Zellweger-Gutknecht, Virgile Perret, Sandra Stupar, Michael Derrer, Cornelia Stengel, Paul Dembinski

TA-SWISS, Foundation for Technology Assessment (Ed.)
vdf Hochschulverlag an der ETH Zürich, 2025.

ISBN 978-3-7281-4209-2

eBook: ISBN 978-3-7281-4210-8

Also available in open access: www.vdf.ch

This abridged version can be downloaded at no cost:
www.ta-swiss.ch

New digital Swiss francs – a brief overview	4
Advantages ...	4
... Disadvantages ...	4
... And a few recommendations	4
Money has always been more than a mere means of payment	5
Functions of money	5
Credit cards, online banking, Twint and other developments	5
Crypto currencies as a new monetary form	6
Decentralised, managed autonomously, programmable – and approximating tangible ownership	6
Focus on digital currencies regulated through financial law	7
New digital Swiss francs – is there a need for Switzerland to take action?	8
How money is issued and circulated in Switzerland	8
Status quo under pressure	9
Design alternatives for new digital Swiss Francs	10
Decentrally managed and secured with double encryption	10
Tokenized deposits: private account in a blockchain	10
Stablecoins: crypto money tied to stable assets	10
Retail CBDCs: central bank digital currency	11
Synthetic CBDCs: private digital Swiss francs, fully covered by the SNB	11
Lugano launches a bold experiment	11
Tokenized deposits – efficient payment transactions, with risk dependent on the banks	12
Automation thanks to smart contracts	12
Subject to existing legislation	12
Stablecoins: efficient store of value or new payment method	13
New forms of payment and business models	13
Potentially secure	14
Digital central bank money: stable and insolvency-proof	14
Retail CBDCs require further reaching regulations for the Swiss National Bank (SNB)	14
Synthetic central bank money – content from both worlds	16
Examples of applications for programmed digital Swiss francs	16
Focus on individual civil liberties	17
Legal provisions depend on the design of the digital money	17
Double-edged transparency	17
Attacks on personal wealth	18
Ecological footprint of money	18
Consensus and control	18
Potentials for a resource-friendly digital Swiss franc	19
Some recommendations concerning digital money in a liberal democracy	20
Priority for the interests of users	20
Digital money should supplement cash, not replace it	20
Need to pay attention to the adaptability of existing legislation	20
Need to establish appeal and arbitration services	20
Need to reduce the ecological footprint of the monetary system	20
Need to take account of scientific findings	20
Advisory group of the project «New Swiss Digital Franks» and project management at TA-SWISS	21

New digital Swiss francs – a brief overview

Crypto currencies such as Bitcoin and the digitalisation of the monetary system in general are a focus of public concern and the subject of headline news. Specialists are examining options for the development of new forms of digital money that can be issued by central banks, commercial banks and private players.

The study focuses on the following four variants of new digital Swiss francs:

- 1 Tokenized deposits
- 2 Stablecoins
- 3 A form of central bank digital currency that would be issued by the Swiss National Bank (retail CBDC)
- 4 A stablecoin that would be covered through central bank money but issued by private players (synthetic CBDC).

These forms of digital money are classified as “new” because they are based on cryptographic technologies. The distinguishing feature of the four forms examined by TA-SWISS in this study is that data regarding their value and structure are stored decentrally in a network comprising a large number of computers. These forms of money are thus rendered largely forgery-proof and emulate material ownership: unlike other data, they cannot be used multiple times simultaneously. In principle, their management and control are also organised decentrally. One of their other special characteristics is that they are programmable, which creates opportunities for new business models, but also gives rise to certain risks.

Advantages ...

New digital Swiss francs offer the prospect of substantial efficiency gains for the economy. Transaction costs would be reduced, and it would be possible to effect transfers in real time – in theory including international transfers if the necessary networking is in place.

Thanks to their programmability, it would be possible to furnish the various forms of new Swiss francs with functionalities that conventional money cannot provide. For example, smart contracts could automatically trigger payments during a commercial pro-

cess as soon as certain conditions have been met. In addition, transactions between machines, as well as models for use-related payments of goods (“pay per use”), would be possible thanks to smart contracts.

Public digital money, as well as synthetic CBDCs secured with central bank money, would be largely insolvency-proof. With the right design, both these forms could help stabilise the monetary system in that they would strengthen people’s trust in the monetary economy.

... Disadvantages ...

Programmed digital Swiss francs could compromise the uniformity of the money. This would be the case if, based on their additional functionalities, new digital Swiss francs would no longer have the same monetary and practical value as otherwise programmed Swiss francs or non-programmed money.

If smart contracts function without human intervention, there is the risk that control – for example, regarding the date and time of the transfer – would no longer be possible. Challenges also arise with respect to the private sphere, especially when programmed money is linked with an identity verification of the holder. In this case it is possible that the holder becomes “transparent”, which could potentially facilitate surveillance by the state. Furthermore, there would also be a greater risk of wrongful use of personal data by private providers.

... And a few recommendations

For the design of new digital Swiss francs the focus should be on the interests of the users, who should have as wide a range of choices as possible.

New digital Swiss francs (whether in the form of stablecoins, tokenized deposits, digital central bank money or synthetic central bank money) should not replace cash, which provides the best protection for the private sphere. Instead, they should be integrated into the existing financial system.

In addition, new digital Swiss francs should also guarantee comprehensive and credible protection of the private sphere.

Switzerland's economic system is based on a liberal, competition-oriented business sector. With regard to the regulation of new digital Swiss francs, the Swiss government should only introduce legal provisions if there is the likelihood of a market failure.

Consultation and arbitration services should be created that advise and support private individuals in the event of disputes with financial institutions.

Issuers of new digital Swiss francs should be required to publish an annual report on the ecological balance of their currency.

Money has always been more than a mere means of payment

The monetary economy has occupied a relatively short space of time in the history of mankind. An accelerated development has taken place in the course of the past fifty years: electronic transactions are increasingly replacing cash payments, and new forms of digital currencies are being developed.

The Guinness Book of Records contains two entries regarding Switzerland's federal mint: one of the golden commemorative coins issued by Swissmint with a diameter of just three millimetres is listed in the 2021 edition as "smallest gold coin in the world". And the Swiss ten-cent coin, which has been minted in unchanged form since 1879, is listed as "oldest coin in the world that is still in circulation".

Money is fascinating – this applies both to the coins and notes in circulation today, as well as to ancient coins discovered during archaeological excavations and which frequently hit the headlines. Money is not only a means of payment, it also represents a political system, a nation, a community.

Functions of money

With the introduction of money, the practice of bartering everyday consumer goods was replaced by a system of commerce based on a standardised value and accounting unit. Money serves several economic purposes: it is simultaneously a means of payment, a store-of-value mechanism and a measure of value. It differs from items such as vouchers, for example, which can be used for acquiring goods or services, but are only valid in selected outlets and only under certain conditions. Under certain circumstances, gold jewellery and works of art can function as store-of-value items, though these can hardly be used for making direct payments.

Money, however, readily fulfils payment as well as store-of-value functions. It also sets a generally applicable standard for the valuation and comparison of (for example) workforce, services and tangible goods, even though the coins, notes and credit balances on bank accounts do not bring any immediate benefits. For this reason, economic sociologists speak of symbolic money, the value of which is based on the confidence placed by people in the monetary economy – guaranteed by the state.

Governments play a significant role in the regulation of the monetary system. In Switzerland, in accordance with the provisions of the Swiss Federal Constitution, monetary sovereignty is in the hands of the federal government, which is also solely responsible for issuing money. It entrusted this task to the Swiss National Bank (SNB, which was founded in 1906) and the federal mint (Swissmint). The responsibilities of the SNB include supplying Switzerland with sufficient money, maintaining the stability of prices and monitoring the infrastructure for payment transactions.

Credit cards, online banking, Twint and other developments

The introduction of credit cards in the 1950s enabled cashless payments and paved the way for the later digitalisation of the monetary economy. In the 1960s, the introduction of ATMs meant that people could obtain cash round the clock, and in the 1980s an increasing number of banks began to provide online services.

With the introduction of smart phones at the turn of the millennium, banking transactions no longer had to be carried out via personal computers, and it was now possible to carry out purchases and sales on the stock market or make payments any time and

anywhere via mobile devices. This paved the way for the age of financial technologies, the so-called “fintechs”. Financial service providers now used the new technologies in order to improve their range of services and develop new ones. An increasing number of private players who had in the past made a name for themselves with high-tech innovations, now began to operate on the financial market.

In Switzerland, a payment service called Twint that was established by a subsidiary of Postfinance commenced operation in 2015. A year later it announced its merger with Paymit, a competitor created by UBS. Today, Twint is the leading provider of mobile payment services in Switzerland, and has succeeded in holding its own against global competitors such as PayPal, Google Pay and Apple Pay.

Crypto currencies as a new monetary form

The first crypto currencies also evolved from the combination of information technology and the monetary system. At the end of the 1990s, various computer security and cryptography experts set out to develop processes by means of which datasets could be stored in blocks that can be continually expanded. This resulted in distributed ledger technology (DLT), which facilitated the decentralised keeping of accounts, and is regarded as the technology that paved the way for the inception of the blockchain – which forms the subject of a 2020 study carried out by TA-SWISS: (“Blockchain – Capabilities, Economic Viability, and the Socio-Technical Environment”).

The blockchain became widely known following the introduction of Bitcoin. What distinguishes crypto currency from conventional money? Crypto currency is a form of electronic money that is generated, brought into circulation and held independently of a central control body. The blockchain provides the necessary infrastructure, comprising a network of interconnected computers which form the network nodes – in the same way as a telephone network, in which the exchanges function as nodes. Communication, respectively data exchange, is carried out via these nodes. Digital wallets installed on mobile phones, or sometimes on PCs, form the terminals of the blockchain. These may be likened to a phone in the telephone network. Protocols with their rules regarding communication and data exchange determine the third component in the blockchain.

In 2019, a project announced by Mark Zuckerberg stunned the financial world. The Facebook founder

planned to develop a global digital payment infrastructure. Here, connection to a basket comprising various currencies was intended to maintain the stability of the crypto currency called “Libra”. According to Zuckerberg, thanks to Libra it would be possible to make carrying out transactions simple and almost free of charge, like sending a WhatsApp message. At that time, with its almost three billion users, Meta already possessed immense market power. In view of this, resistance from political and business circles was correspondingly fierce. Under international pressure, Meta gradually curtailed its plans until in 2022 it definitively pulled the plug on the project, which it had meanwhile renamed “Diem”.

Decentralised, managed autonomously, programmable – and approximating tangible ownership

New digital forms of money possess four fundamental characteristics. One of these is their decentralised organisation, which means that decision-making powers and control are distributed among several parties who are independent of one another. This represents a major difference in comparison with the conventional monetary system, in which the banks act as intermediaries.

This means that DLT grants users a degree of autonomy that has never before existed in the monetary system. While in the past it was not possible to access conventional investments without the involvement of the banks (or at least their infrastructure), users can now autonomously manage the digital money stored in their network. This means it is possible to directly effect payments between private individuals bilaterally (P2P), without the intervention of a bank. At the same time, DLT also enables non-regulated players to generate their own digital money.

In addition, digital money is also programmable. Here, rules and conditions can be programmed directly into the monetary units. Furthermore, with DLT it is also possible to carry out automated actions with the aid of smart contracts, for example in that payments can be triggered automatically and on a step-by-step basis during the course of a transaction. Thanks to its programmability, digital money facilitates functions that do not exist with conventional money, and also creates options for new services and business models. However, programmability can also give rise to new risks. It could result in the loss of the basic function of money as a generally valid and accepted means of payment, or place the private sphere under pressure.

Digital money can be equated with tangible ownership in that the holder can autonomously control it and gain exclusive access to it. This approximation of ownership of digital money places the holder in a privileged position, towards both the issuer of the online money and the general public. Unlike a text in the Internet, digital money cannot be copied and used multiple times, either by the holder or by third parties.

Focus on digital currencies regulated through financial law

In the meantime around a thousand crypto currencies have been created, of which Bitcoin, Ethereum and Tether are the most widely known. Digital money is created outside the scope of the regulated monetary system, and depending on how decentrally it is generated, it is not possible to identify the issuer.

Bitcoin and other crypto currencies are already being intensively studied, and the volume of associated specialised literature is constantly increasing. In

its study, “Blockchain – Capabilities, Economic Viability, and the Socio-Technical Environment”, TA-SWISS examined Bitcoin in detail. But in the study summarised here, it focused on digital money that is generated by private but state-regulated players, or by the state itself, respectively the Swiss National Bank.

The study, “New digital Swiss francs”, was carried out in an interdisciplinary cooperation between six research institutions from the German-speaking and French-speaking regions of Switzerland, with representatives from the fields of economic sociology, political science, ethics, finance, law and economics, under the leadership of Corinne Zellweger-Gutknecht, professor of private law and commercial law at the University of Basel. The methodological concept of the study was based on a review of the existing scientific literature, interviews with specialists, a focus group and a broad-based online survey of the population. An independent quality control of the study was assured by an external advisory group of experts; the names are listed in the publishing details.

New digital Swiss francs – is there a need for Switzerland to take action?

The Swiss franc is often referred to as “Alpine gold”, and the banks are regarded by some as icons of our country, and by others as hostile institutions. It is a fact that the finance sector is a key component of Switzerland’s economy. The new digital currencies open up opportunities for new services and business models, but at the same time they also put pressure on the conventional distribution of tasks between the various players in the finance sector and the latter’s established working methods.

In Switzerland, people still like to use cash as a means of payment. But in the past few years, the proportion of payments in cash has fallen sharply: in 2017, for example, cash was used for around 70 percent of transactions, and by 2020 this figure had fallen to 43 percent. Then 2024 represented a turning point in that, for the first time, payments via mobile phone apps occupied first place with 26.8 percent, closely followed by the use of debit cards (26.2 percent) and payments with notes and coins (25.7 percent). Despite the clear decline in the importance of cash for effecting payments, many still consider it to be indispensable: in various surveys, the proportion of people who are opposed to the abolition of notes and coins remains stable at over two-thirds. Cash is often regarded as a store of value: according to the results of such surveys, during periods of negative interest rates many people like to keep cash reserves in safe deposit boxes.

Cash also remains a topic of political debate, as the people’s initiative calling for an independent Swiss currency with coins or banknotes (“cash is freedom”) submitted on 15 February 2023, indicates. The Federal Council has formulated a direct counterproposal to this initiative.

How money is issued and circulated in Switzerland

The public sector issues three forms of money in Switzerland: coins, banknotes and sight deposits on accounts at the Swiss National Bank (SNB). SNB sight deposits are held by commercial banks and other financial market participants (typically, insurances), who are thus clients of the SNB. Via the interest on

sight deposits the SNB influences the money market interest rate.

One of the tasks of commercial banks is to bring money into circulation. In simple terms, new money is created in that the commercial banks grant credits to their clientèle. Here, a credit note is issued on the borrower’s account. Then in the bank’s internal accounts the amount concerned is reported under liabilities. Over time, the money disappears from the borrower’s account, for example because it is invested in the construction of a house or in a business. However, it remains in the monetary system until it is used somewhere in order to repay a loan to a bank, or buy assets such as shares, or obtain cash from the bank.

Amounts that are paid in to their accounts by clients are also shown in the internal accounts of commercial banks as liabilities towards their clients. This form of liability is partially covered through the sight deposits that the commercial bank is required to hold at the SNB. The bank deposits are secured up to the amount of 100,000 Swiss francs. Deposits that exceed this amount are subject to a bankruptcy risk, the level of which varies according to the bank’s business model. In addition, an upper limit exists for the deposits secured in the banking system. This limit is set at around 8 billion Swiss francs, i.e. only around 1.8 percent of the approximately 500 billion held on all savings accounts, which would already be insufficient in the event of a bankruptcy of a medium-sized bank.

The loss of the clientèle’s confidence, for example due to bad management decisions or a generally uncertain economic environment, can propel a bank into insolvency. The possibility is very high that clients could storm the counters and demand their money because the risk of loss increases, the longer the deposits remain in the bank. Ultimately, a bank run could itself drive a financial institution to ruin as a self-fulfilling prophecy.

Status quo under pressure

The Swiss franc is strong, payment transactions generally run smoothly, and clients in Switzerland have various means at their disposal for carrying out banking business and transactions. So in the view of the Federal Council, new digital forms of money issued by the state do not offer any additional benefits. Instead, it is primarily concerned about the risks that in particular digital central bank money could pose for the money market and financial stability. The Federal Council is therefore highly reluctant to develop a digital Swiss franc issued by the state. Its preference is to adhere to the fundamental principle of the market economy and leave it up to private players to develop new digital forms of money.

Other countries are also cautious. To date, no industrialised nation has issued digital central bank money. In the autumn, the Bank of Canada – a pioneer in this field – suspended its work on such a project and instead focused on improving its payments system. Three emerging nations, in which access to banking services is often restricted – as a result of which digital money issued by the state was intended to offer a remedy – have made slightly more progress. In the past few years, the Bahamas, Nigeria and Jamaica have issued digital central bank money, though very little use has been made of these digital currencies.

Nonetheless, even if no western industrialised nation has issued a digital currency of its own to date, there are plenty of ongoing research and pilot projects. In this regard, the activities of the European Union are at an advanced stage. In 2021, the European Central Bank (ECB) initiated a study phase concerning the concept of a digital euro (D€), and this process was concluded in October 2023. The ECB Governing Council then resolved to launch a preparatory phase lasting approximately two years, at the end of which a decision is to be taken regarding the possible introduction of a D€.

Confidence as a key factor

In the online survey, in which 1,212 people aged between 15 and 79 from the three main language regions of Switzerland participated, confirmed the existing sympathy for cash: 63 percent of the respondents stated they use cash at least once a week. The use of debit cards and mobile phone apps is somewhat lower: here, 59, respectively 53, percent of the respondents stated they use these at least once a week. For payments, crypto currencies are practically irrelevant. Baby boomers and people born prior to 1980 use cash more frequently than representatives of later generations, who use cards and payment apps more often.

More than half the respondents (53 percent) are unfamiliar with the digital versions of central bank money (CBDC). An even higher proportion of respondents (67 percent) have never heard of initiatives aimed at creating CBDCs. The results of the survey can be interpreted against this backdrop.

With regard to the question of who should issue digital money, the Swiss National Bank enjoys the confidence of around 70 percent of the respondents. By contrast, confidence in Fintech and other private sector issuers is extremely low – only around two percent of the respondents place their trust in these bodies. If state digital money were to be introduced, roughly 40 percent of the respondents declared they would use it; the probability of use is significantly higher in Ticino than in the other regions. In the view of the respondents, the most important requirements to be met with respect to state-issued digital money are trustworthiness of the provider, data protection, stability and simplicity of use.

In Switzerland, people know very little about CBDCs compared with the populations of other countries. It is thus all the more important to encourage a balanced discussion in Switzerland on the potential introduction of digital money issued by the Swiss National Bank or private players.

Design alternatives for new digital Swiss Francs

In recent years, crypto currencies have primarily hit the headlines due to their enormous price fluctuations. With new digital Swiss francs, protection and supervision of the issuers would ensure stability and security. The TA-SWISS study identifies four possible alternatives for the structure of new digital Swiss francs.

Money in electronic form is nothing new. Conventional account balances are compiled electronically and stored on the secured servers of the respective commercial banks. The account information is provided on the computer chip that is embedded in the account holder's debit or credit card, and various hardware-based security mechanisms protect access to the account.

Decentrally managed and secured with double encryption

By contrast, digital money based on distributed ledger technology (DLT) exists, as already noted above, exclusively in the form of data that are decentrally stored on multiple computers in a network. This crypto-based money is managed via digital wallets – i.e. apps which function as a gateway to the blockchain. They store, modify and transmit the access data to the digital values, but not the values themselves. Access to the blockchain is encoded by a private and a public key; both keys are required for transactions via the Internet and both are stored in the wallet. As long as the existing encryption procedures cannot be hacked by quantum computers, payments with digital wallets are very secure, and in any case more so than payments with debit and credit cards.

Numerous crypto currencies created by private players, such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, Tether and many others, are currently not subject to any official control mechanisms and are highly speculative. As noted above, these currencies are not the subject of this TA-SWISS study, which focuses on digital money issued by state-supervised private players (tokenized bank deposits, stablecoins and synthetic CBDCs) or the Swiss National Bank (retail CBDCs).

Tokenized deposits: private account in a blockchain

Various commercial banks are currently considering how they could issue crypto-based money for their clients, but to date no uniform procedure has been established.

Banks could create tokens by depicting their clients' deposits cryptographically. For their clients, this would merely change the technical depiction of their deposit, but not the deposit itself. The latter would remain a claim on the part of the client towards the bank for cash payment or transfer. It would be covered by the assets on the bank's balance sheet and would be subject to the bankruptcy risk described above. But in that these tokenized deposits would be stored on a programmable platform of the bank, they could to some extent be used for similar purposes such as stablecoins.

Stablecoins: crypto money tied to stable assets

While "classical" crypto currencies such as Bitcoin are subject to substantial fluctuations, stablecoins are considerably less volatile. This is because their price is tied to a reference value via a protection mechanism – usually, a state currency, a currency basket, or other assets such as precious metals. This practice is often based on the fact that the issuers invest the money, which they receive for the issue of their stablecoins, in reference values as coverage, and agree to take back the stablecoins at the request of their clients and to repay the proceeds from the sale of the collateral. If the reference values exist outside the blockchain, they are referred to as off-chain collateral, whereas online-collateralised stablecoins are tied to values within the blockchain. The TA-SWISS study focused exclusively on off-chain collateralised stablecoins.

10 Retail CBDCs: central bank digital currency

CBDC stands for central bank digital currency. If it is only used by certain financial market players, i.e. at the wholesale level, it is referred to as wholesale CBDC. The TA-SWISS study did not deal with this form of digital currency. Instead, it focused on CBDCs that would be available to the public, i.e. at the retail level, and are thus referred to as retail CBDCs.

A digital Swiss franc would belong in this category and be issued by the Swiss National Bank (SNB). The TA-SWISS study also only examined retail CBDCs that would be distributed to the public via the banks and other players. Thus the profile of retail CBDCs largely corresponds to that of cash, and for this reason they are sometimes referred to as “digital cash”. The clientèle would have direct access to SNB money, though the SNB itself would not be required to maintain client relationships with private individuals.

By contrast, the TA-SWISS study did not examine retail CBDCs for which everyone would be able to open an account at the SNB, because here the latter’s role would fundamentally change. The existing structure of the SNB does not include the prerequisites for maintaining relationships with a private clientèle, and thus for meeting the associated technical demands and obligations of due care.

4 Synthetic CBDCs: private digital Swiss francs, fully covered by the SNB

Synthetic central bank digital currency (synthetic CBDC) is another form of new digital Swiss francs. Here the term “synthetic” stands for “artificial” in that a synthetic CBDC does not take the form of “genuine” central bank digital currency, because although it is fully collateralised by the SNB, it is issued by commercial banks or other private players. In this model, a digital Swiss franc corresponds to a real, “analogue” Swiss franc in terms of value. Even if the issuing commercial bank should become insolvent, the holders of synthetic CBDCs would not suffer any loss, and instead could transfer their credit balance covered by the SNB to another financial institution.

Lugano launches a bold experiment

Municipal payment tokens are not CBDCs, but are a form of state-issued digital money. They cannot be classified as CBDCs because they are issued by a municipality rather than a central bank. In 2020, as the first public-law issuer in Switzerland, the city of Lugano issued a digital payment token called LVGA. The declared objective of this move is to inform the public about the use of digital currencies and promote local retail trade. The LVGA can only be used for payments of goods and services in around four hundred partner organisations. It cannot be used for paying taxes or other levies because this would take away liquidity from businesses.

Tokenized deposits – efficient payment transactions, with risk dependent on the banks

As the designation indicates, tokenized deposits are close to the conventional system with bank accounts. This means they can easily be integrated into the existing monetary system.

Tokenized deposits offer the prospect of seamlessly carrying out transactions across national and currency borders in real time that do not need a central exchange. This would significantly increase the efficiency of commercial payment transactions between companies, as well as within the banking world.

Tokenized deposits can streamline business processes, but they do not notably change the underlying system, because they are merely deposits that are depicted in a distributed ledger structure. They are therefore exposed to the same insolvency risks as existing bank deposits. Furthermore, tokens would not permit direct payments between private individuals.

Automation thanks to smart contracts

Thanks to tokenized deposits it would be simpler to integrate smart contracts into the banking system and enable changes in client relationships to be effected automatically. This can be illustrated using the following fictitious example: smart electricity meters would be able to measure their own consumption and communicate the reading directly to the energy supplier. This would enable the more efficient processing of payments, and would contribute towards the automation and simplification of processes. At the same time, such transactions would also be associated with certain risks: because they would be carried out automatically and without direct human supervision, they could be susceptible to various security threats.

Alongside beneficial efficiency gains, this thought experiment also indicates a risk that goes hand in hand with such automation mechanisms: depending on their structure, they thwart rule-of-law institutions which normally protect the weaker party. Without suitable protective measures, this technology could have an adverse effect on fair relations within a business partnership.

Subject to existing legislation

The fact that tokenized deposits primarily differ from conventional bank deposits in terms of storage method means that their security is regulated by existing legislation: issuers of deposit tokens require a banking licence and are subject to the supervision of the Swiss Federal Financial Market Supervisory Authority (FINMA). In the event that the issuing financial institution should become bankrupt, insolvency legislation and the general provisions governing bankruptcy would be applicable.

The fundamental legal challenges that arise with respect to digital money and smart contracts are dealt with in the section on legal issues (page 17).

Stablecoins: efficient store of value or new payment method

Stablecoins open up a variety of options – depending on how they are structured, they are suitable as a means of value storage or can be used for payment transactions.

Stablecoins can be issued by private individuals as well as by commercial banks. In Switzerland there are currently four stablecoins denominated in Swiss francs for private clients. The respective numbers of involved holders are between 50 and around 1200. These four Swiss franc stablecoins have a centralised characteristic in that they are issued by institutions that are identifiable. They thus differ from decentrally organised stablecoins, the issuers of which cannot be identified. There are currently no licensed Swiss banks that issue stablecoins for the general public.

Stablecoins are still lacking in terms of security and comfort of use, which means they cannot compete with conventional payment methods. This could change in the future, although it is not yet clear in which direction further developments are likely to take place.

Stablecoins can be expected to prevail if they succeed in reducing delays and minimising the costs of transactions, and thus in exploiting the greatest weaknesses of the existing system. In particular they could utilise their strengths in the area of transactions across national and currency borders. They also offer the prospect of beneficial solutions for transfers between private individuals – even in the case

of very small amounts. Here, for example, someone who does not want to pay an annual subscription for a journal could use stablecoins to pay the moderate price for an individual article, quickly and conveniently, and without incurring transaction costs.

If payment transactions were to be shifted to stablecoins, this would have consequences for the banks, whose viability would be reduced due to the decline in their commission income.

New forms of payment and business models

In the same way as tokens, stablecoins can also be used for smart contracts. These would be suitable for business models, which for example make a payment dependent on the actual use of an ordered item or service. This might apply to the usage-related invoicing of a loan-financed photocopier: here the company only has to repay the loan after the sensors have registered the fact that the photocopier is in use. To date, business models of this type have failed due to the high transaction costs associated with conventional payment methods.

With the Internet of Things, the demand for machine-to-machine payments is increasing, and here too, smart contracts with stablecoins would be a suitable option. The concept of a smart refrigerator, which uses sensors to register the fact that, for example, the quantity of milk is low, and subse-

quently autonomously orders and pays for a new carton from the grocery store via the Internet, is a potentially groundbreaking but as yet fictitious model. The already cited example of payment of electricity bills is closer to reality: thanks to the use of smart meters, it is already possible today to automatically record a household's electricity consumption. The data are currently read by the network operator, which then submits its bill. In the future, it would be possible for smart electricity meters to communicate directly with the network operator and issue a bill without human intervention. While business models of this sort are attractive in view of their efficiency, they also give rise to certain risks. If they are not supervised, their security could be compromised. Furthermore, personal data could get into the wrong hands and it is possible that control over the date and time of the payment could be lost.

Potentially secure

If stablecoins were to be issued by a financial institution with a good reputation, this could encourage many people to convert their bank deposits into

stablecoins. This would have consequences for the financial system, especially if people from other countries were to convert their deposits in a foreign currency into Swiss franc stablecoins. As a safe haven currency, the Swiss franc would become even more attractive, and this would increase the challenges for economic and monetary policy.

Restricting access to Swiss franc stablecoins to residents only could be a possible counter-measure. In this case, the stablecoin would have to be designed so that buyers can be identified. In addition, a restriction to a domestic clientèle would conflict with the fundamental global reach of stablecoins.

Another counter-measure could be imposed by the banks. If they were to raise their interest rates to a level that reflects the risks, this would make bank deposits better able to compete with the attractive interest rates attached to stablecoins. Thus it would be possible to counteract the challenges that stablecoins could bring about for monetary policy, not only with interventionist solutions targeting their design, but also with market instruments such as interest rates appropriate to the level of risk.

Digital central bank money: stable and insolvency-proof

If the Swiss National Bank were to issue digital money for the general public, the money concerned would be insolvency-proof. In addition, its attractiveness for potential investors would be substantial.

Digital central bank money in the form of retail CBDC would be issued by the Swiss National Bank and subsequently used and brought into circulation independently by the commercial banks. This means that retail CBDCs have a similar risk profile to that of cash and are insolvency-proof.

Retail CBDCs require further reaching regulations for the Swiss National Bank (SNB)

The SNB's mandate is currently limited to issuing cash. The creation of a retail CBDC would therefore require an extension of its mandate. The Federal Act on Currency and Payment Instruments specifies the requirements the SNB has to meet when issuing

money; These requirements would no longer suffice for the SNB to issue a retail CBDC. Other aspects that would have to be regulated would include the functionality of a digital Swiss franc, as well as the necessary infrastructure and the involved players; alongside the SNB and commercial banks, the latter would include the system operators, other service providers and the clientèle.

A digital Swiss franc issued by the SNB would not be attractive solely for Swiss customers. It would also appeal to an international clientèle, as long as access to it would not be restricted. The question as to which persons outside Switzerland would be permitted to acquire retail CBDCs is something that would have to be discussed: can everyone who wants to park money in Switzerland buy retail CBDCs, or is this restricted to those who carry out investments in Swiss francs?

A broadening of the client base also goes hand in hand with higher control requirements. In order to prevent money laundering and other unlawful activ-

ities, the SNB would have to create the necessary resources and supervisory structures. Furthermore, strong demand for a retail CBDC could have an adverse effect on the stability of the Swiss financial system. This would be the case if a large number of people were to convert their conventional deposits into retail CBDCs within a short period of time, thereby causing a digital bank run.

When designing retail CBDCs, various options exist for limiting their attractiveness. Here, for example, the decision could be taken to waive the payment of interest on retail CBDCs so that conventional interest-bearing bank deposits would remain competitive – in any case when the banks pay interest on deposits that sufficiently reflects the risk associated with the banking business. Other design-related options would be feasible, for example a phased introduction of limited quantities of retail CBDCs that would be increased on a gradual basis. This would also

make it possible to gradually gain experience with the new digital money.

A digital Swiss franc issued by the SNB could however also contribute towards increased stability of the financial system. The insolvency-proof design of retail CBDCs would generally strengthen the clientèle's confidence in the monetary system and thus reduce the risk of bank runs. In addition, a retail CBDC could have a disciplining influence on the banks in that, due to the impact of the new money, they could endeavour to render their own business model more secure and avoid excessive risks, or would have to pay adequate interest on them.

In the same way as a synthetic CBDC (see below), a retail CBDC would open up opportunities for innovation that could benefit the entire economy.

Synthetic central bank money – content from both worlds

Unlike retail CBDCs, synthetic CBDCs would not be issued by the Swiss National Bank (SNB), but rather by commercial banks or other players subject to regulation under financial market law. For the creation of synthetic CBDCs, the SNB would have to anticipate fewer regulatory adjustments than would be the case with retail CBDCs. At the same time, synthetic CBDCs would be fully covered by central bank money and thus also protected against insolvency.

The established structures of the commercial banks would benefit synthetic CBDCs for public business. There would probably be additional providers of synthetic CBDCs (also regulated and supervised by the state). Furthermore, competition between these financial intermediaries can be expected to positively influence both the degree of efficiency and the flexibility of use of the new money. On the other hand, synthetic CBDCs would continue to be associated with the operational risks of their issuers.

The attractiveness of synthetic CBDCs for clients from Switzerland and throughout the world would be similar to that of retail CBDCs. It is therefore conceivable that bank deposits could be reallocated to synthetic CBDCs, with the associated consequences for the financial system. Here, too, market economy instruments such as the application of a risk-adapted (i.e. higher) interest rate on conventional deposits, could act as a counter-measure. Legally speaking, synthetic CBDCs would be governed by private law, but issuers would be subject to supervisory regulation.

Examples of applications for programmed digital Swiss francs

All four forms of new digital Swiss francs share a common feature, namely that they are programmable and could potentially contain new functions. The state could exploit this, for example by integrating digital identity solutions into the payment process. For the purpose of an alcohol purchase or payment of a ticket for a horror film, for example, the customer's identity would be automatically checked in order to determine whether he or she is old enough.

Critics warn against possible state influence through programmable digital money. It would be possible to program digital money in order to block purchases of certain goods or favour (or exclude) a selected clientèle. The state would theoretically be placed in a position in which it could influence people's purchasing habits, for example by increasing the price of fuels through correspondingly programmed digital money as a measure against climate change, or preventing the purchase of foodstuffs containing fat and sugar in order to combat obesity. It would also be conceivable for the state to tie the use of digital money in some situations to specified conditions, or to exclude people from its use due to certain characteristics.

As described below, using digital money in order to achieve political and social objectives would neither be permissible nor purposeful. Firstly, this would circumvent the processes of democratic legitimation. And secondly, this could influence the uniformity of the money. One of its principal characteristics, namely its exchangeability, would be lost if the value of its units were to no longer be uniform.

Focus on individual civil liberties

New digital Swiss francs could assume a variety of organisational and structural forms. This means the need for regulation also varies accordingly. Programmability, which characterises all forms of tokenized money, places a significant challenge on the protection of the private sphere.

Switzerland's economic system is based on a liberal, competition-oriented business sector: in accordance with Article 94 of the Swiss Federal Constitution, "The federal government and the cantons shall abide by the principle of economic freedom. They shall safeguard the interests of the Swiss economy as a whole and, together with the private sector, shall contribute to the welfare and economic security of the population." Thus state interventions are only permissible if they benefit the welfare of the population and protect economic freedom. In other words, the state should only intervene in the market with regulatory measures if the market itself is unable to deliver the desired economic and social outcomes.

Legal provisions depend on the design of the digital money

As described above, the four forms of new digital Swiss francs differ in terms of the role of the commercial banks, the SNB and private players. The four variants also differ from one another in terms of the deployed mechanisms for securing the value of digital Swiss francs. This would also be reflected in the different additional regulatory requirements for the four models.

The current provisions of monetary law contain very few technical and logistical regulations. If new digital Swiss francs were to be issued, more detailed provisions would be required. Here, it would in particular be necessary to specify the design and functionalities of the digital money and define the roles of the respective players.

In addition, the legal nature of new digital Swiss francs would also require clarification. For example, the provisions of the Swiss Civil Code relating to property rights and ownership refer to tangible objects. The question as to whether, and to what extent, money in digital form can legally assume a similar position to that of tangible objects, has yet to be examined.

Double-edged transparency

The programmability of crypto currency opens up opportunities for innovative business models, but it also gives rise to risks for the private sphere and individual civil liberties, to which Switzerland as a liberal democracy is strongly committed.

One of the associated challenges concerns the fact that digital money potentially facilitates extensive insights into the private sphere of its users, or simplifies misuse of the collected data. In the context of social scores in particular, the risk could arise that the private sphere and individual freedoms of users could be significantly curtailed: if transactions are evaluated on the basis of personal characteristics, the possibility cannot be ruled out that private companies or even the state – including through regulation vis-à-vis private issuers – could discriminate against people due to such evaluations, cut them off from access to certain services, or otherwise disadvantage them.

Programmed digital money with integrated identification elements could be suitable for verifying people's age: here it would be possible, for example, to prevent minors from accessing subscription-based pornography websites or other problematic content, or to reserve certain services for local residents or people of a particular nationality. At the same time, however, the risk arises that this form of individually assignable money could make the people concerned "transparent" in that all of their transactions would be traceable and could be monitored by the state.

Private-sector companies could also be tempted to use such personal data in order to tailor their products to the profiles of their clientèle, and potentially to exclude certain groups of people from their product range right from the start. This would be in contradiction to the principles specified in the Swiss Federal Constitution, according to which the highest degree of equal opportunity must be assured between all people, and no one may be subjected to discrimination.

Risks of this nature have to be counteracted by providing greater protection of the private sphere. Users have to be able to retain control over their data and not be patronised by money. Data protection must be comprehensively guaranteed.

Attacks on personal wealth

Critics also express the concern that, thanks to digital money, the state could find it easier to impose negative interest rates for wide client circles (thanks in particular to retail CBDCs). This would be equivalent to indirect expropriation of citizens, whose assets would subsequently lose value.

Unlawful acts against (state) digital money, i.e. the hacking of wallets, would also have to be anticipated. Here the Swiss Penal Code would come

into play: Article 143 stipulates that any person or persons who for their own unlawful gain obtain for themselves data stored in a data processing system and which is not intended for them and has been specially secured to prevent unauthorised access is liable to a custodial sentence or a monetary penalty. As already noted, the protection of data stored in wallets is especially strong. Whether it will be possible to counteract the foreseeable decryption options through technical measures with a quantum computer, or if regulatory adjustments could become necessary, remains to be seen.

Ecological footprint of money

Every form of money requires resources. How much energy is required depends partly on the means of payment deployed by users, but also on the method for processing transactions.

The production of a Swiss bank note places high demands on technology and material: the notes in the existing series comprise a plastic core coated on both sides with cotton. Special foils with kinematic structures are integrated, which depict a different pattern depending on the viewing angle. Special security dyes are used for the printing process. According to the SNB, Swiss banknotes account for an annual level of greenhouse gas emissions of around 1,900 CO₂ equivalents, which corresponds to the emissions from a Swiss village with 300 inhabitants. The production of the bank notes accounts for 82 percent of the burden on the environment, while the remaining 18 percent is attributable to logistics and waste disposal.

If the use of crypto-based currencies were to increase, the SNB would probably have to provide less money. However, “intangible” crypto currency also consumes resources: energy, as well as hardware for storage devices and terminals. The TA-SWISS study did not set out to compare the ecological footprint of cash with that of digital currencies, not the least because the latter are intended to complement cash, not to replace it.

Consensus and control

In the case of crypto-based currency, the value of which is stored decentrally in a distributed ledger structure, each node manages a copy of the register and determines whether a modification is correct. This calls for a consensus mechanism that ensures that harmony exists between the nodes.

The older “proof-of-work” mechanism used, for example, for Bitcoin requires an enormous quantity of energy. With this process, the validators at the nodes in the network compete with one another in that they have to solve a difficult cryptographic puzzle in order to – as a form of “reward” – be able to validate a transaction. In 2024, solely for the operation of the Bitcoin network an estimated 0.6 percent of the entire global consumption of electricity was required, which is equivalent to the electricity consumption of a medium-sized country. In addition, there is the problem of a huge quantity of electronic waste, because people who want to carry out the validation process need the latest generation of ultra-high-performance computers, which they utilise to an enormous extent. It is estimated that the Bitcoin network produces as much electronic waste as the whole of the Netherlands.

By contrast, the “proof-of-stake” process does not depend on high-performance computers. Instead, the validators are selected on the basis of the number of tokens they possess and which they are willing to use as collateral. This approach rewards the validators according to their share in the net-

work. The estimated annual electricity consumption of proof-of-stake processes is roughly equivalent to that of a small US town with around 2,100 households, i.e. is many times below that of high-consumption proof-of-work mechanisms.

Alongside the consensus processes, the number of nodes and their distance from one another also influence the energy requirement of distributed ledger systems. In those cases in which only selected nodes are eligible for validation, the electricity consumption is lower in comparison with those in which all nodes can be validated. This is because when a lower number of nodes are to be validated there are fewer redundancies, and thus lower electricity consumption. With such a DLT system with few nodes subject to approval, the energy requirement for transactions is also lower than that of many conventional systems with credit cards.

Potentials for a resource-friendly digital Swiss franc

New digital Swiss francs, which are based on a proof-of-stake mechanism with a low number of nodes, could under certain circumstances also be more energy-efficient, and thus more environment-friendly in comparison with existing payment systems. In addition, with DLT systems the possibility exists to bundle payments, which further reduces their energy requirement.

Finally, for making an ecological assessment of new digital Swiss francs, the source from which the necessary energy is obtained also plays a role. If they are generated in a country with a high proportion of green power, this reduces their ecological footprint. Thus there are various possibilities for adjusting the sustainability of the monetary system with new digital Swiss francs.

Some recommendations concerning digital money in a liberal democracy

New digital Swiss francs can increase the efficiency of the monetary system, open up new business opportunities and broaden the users' options and scope for action, providing that certain principles are adhered to.

The established economic freedom in Switzerland goes hand in hand with a commitment by the state to ensure the most competition-friendly conditions. At the same time, the state should only intervene at the regulatory level if there are signs of a market failure.

Priority for the interests of users

Users should not have to adjust to the technology. Instead, the latter should be oriented on the needs of the population. People should be able to choose their money themselves, and thus decide the extent to which they want to protect their private sphere.

Digital money should supplement cash, not replace it

In view of the security and high level of protection of the private sphere ensured by cash, new digital Swiss francs should supplement it, not replace it. The introduction of such crypto-based forms of money which protect the private sphere would additionally broaden people's range of choices.

Need to pay attention to the adaptability of existing legislation

New digital Swiss francs can be structured in different ways, and thanks to their programmability they contain a variety of functionalities. Consequently, their users would be better served with basic provisions in the Swiss Code of Obligations that can be adapted by the involved parties, than with unduly complex, mandatory and highly detailed financial market regulations.

Need to establish appeal and arbitration services

Smart contracts and programmed money give rise to new business relationships between money providers and their clientèle. Appeal and arbitration services should be established so that people can refer to them in the event of disputes with financial players.

Need to reduce the ecological footprint of the monetary system

The requirements of existing and future forms of money for energy and other resources vary considerably, depending on their structure. Issuers of new digital Swiss francs should be required to publish an annual report on the ecological balance of their money. Energy-saving validation processes should be given preference over proof-of-work mechanisms.

Need to take account of scientific findings

Crypto-based forms of money have been intensively researched at the international level for a number of years. With respect to the design and introduction of new digital Swiss francs – whether in the form of tokenized deposits, stablecoins, retail CBDCs, synthetic CBDCs or as yet unknown forms – scientific findings should be taken into account right from the start.

Advisory group of the project «New Swiss Digital Franks»

- **Dr. Stefan Vannoni**, economist, Director of cemsuisse, chairman of the advisory group, member of the Steering Committee of TA-SWISS
- **Dr. Romain Baeriswyl**, Deputy Head of Monetary Policy Analysis, Economic Affairs, Swiss National Bank
- **Markus Brönnimann**, data protection officer, canton of Basel-Landschaft
- **Pascale Bruderer**, founder of Swiss Stablecoin, former member of the National Council and the Council of States
- **Prof. Dr. Mirjam Eggen**, professor for private law, University of Bern
- **Dr. Martin Hess**, head of economic policy, Swiss Banking
- **Margit Himmel**, head of the Monetary Policy and Economy section, Swiss Federal Finance Administration
- **Mathias Imbach**, CEO of Sygnum Bank
- **Dr. David Iselin**, curator of the Money Unleashed exhibition at Bern Historical Museum
- **Jörg Mäder**, IT specialist, member of the town council of Opfikon (Green Liberal Party of Switzerland, GLP), former member of the National Council
- **Thomas Müller**, science journalist, member of the Steering Committee of TA-SWISS
- **Dr. Inke Nyborg**, research associate at the Institute for Banking and Finance, University of Zurich
- **Dr. Samuel Schmassmann**, economist at the Monetary Policy and Economy section, Swiss Federal Finance Administration
- **Babette Sigg**, President of the Consumers Forum
- **Dr. Tobias Trütsch**, Managing Director, Centre for Financial Services at the University of St Gallen

Projectmanagement at TA-SWISS

- **Dr. Elisabeth Ehrensperger**, managing director
- **Dr. Laetitia Ramelet**, project manager
- **Fabian Schluemp**, communication

Impressum

In the network of online money

Condensed version of the project «New digital Swiss francs»

TA-SWISS, Bern 2025

TA 85A/2025

Author: Dr. Lucienne Rey, TA-SWISS, Bern

Translation: Keith Hewlett, Transcripta AG

Production: Dr. Laetitia Ramelet and Fabian Schluep, TA-SWISS, Bern

Layout and graphics: Hannes Saxer, Bern

Printed by: Jordi AG – Das Medienhaus, Belp

TA-SWISS – Foundation for Technology Assessment

New technology often leads to decisive improvements in the quality of our lives. At the same time, however, it involves new types of risks whose consequences are not always predictable. The Foundation for Technology Assessment TA-SWISS examines the potential advantages and risks of new technological developments in the fields of life sciences and medicine, digitalisation and society as well as energy and environment. The studies carried out by the Foundation are aimed at the decision-making bodies in politics and the economy, as well as at the general public. In addition, TA-SWISS promotes the exchange of information and opinions between specialists in science, economics and politics and the public at large through participatory processes. Studies conducted and commissioned by the Foundation are aimed at providing objective, independent, and broad-based information on the advantages and risks of new technologies. To this purpose the studies are conducted in collaboration with groups comprised of experts in the relevant fields. The professional expertise of the supervisory groups covers a broad range of aspects of the issue under study.

The Foundation TA-SWISS is a centre for excellence of the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences.

TA-SWISS
Foundation for Technology Assessment
Brunngasse 36
CH-3011 Bern
info@ta-swiss.ch
www.ta-swiss.ch

